

STUDIES IN THE CHEMISTRY OF TELLURIUM. PART I. THE BEHAVIOUR OF TELLURIUM ON CATHODIC AND ANODIC POLARISATION

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The behaviour of the massive tellurium electrode on cathodic, followed by anodic polarisation, has been studied in 0.1N-H₂SO₄, in buffer solutions of p_H 4.98 and 7.02 and in 0.1 N-NaOH. The curves exhibit initial jumps in potential without showing breaks, both on anodic and cathodic polarisation before passing to regions of constant potentials. The potentials at the plateaus of the cathodic and the anodic regions and also the decay potentials vary with p_H and current density. The Tafel lines constructed from time—potential curves possess higher slopes than those directly measured. The Tafel lines obtained in 0.1N-H₂SO₄ possess two slopes amounting to $\sim$ 0.04 and 0.07 to 0.118 v, indicating that the evolution of hydrogen is governed by an electrochemical mechanism. Anions have no effect on the Tafel line slopes at low current density.

In a previous investigation we studied the behaviour of chromium metal on cathodic, followed by anodic polarisation. Such a study reveals that chromium possesses a large tendency to assume the passive condition, especially on applying the anodic current (Issa, Ammar and Khalifa, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 492). It was also found that the behaviour of tellurium in buffer solutions, initially free from the metal ions, can be correlated with the tendency of the element to show signs of passivation (Tourky *et al.*, unpublished). The aim of the present investigation is to study the behaviour of tellurium on cathodic and anodic polarisation with a view to throwing more light on the problem. We also investigated the hydrogen overpotential on tellurium cathodes in sulphuric acid solutions of different concentrations and in buffer solutions of different p_H .

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions.—The time—potential curves were traced in the course of cathodic and anodic polarisation in 0.1 N-H₂SO₄, in buffer solutions of p_H 4.98 and 7.02 and in 0.1 N-NaOH solution.

The Tafel lines were constructed in H₂SO₄ solutions ranging from 5 N to 0.01 N, in buffer solutions covering the p_H range 3 to 12 and in 0.1N-NaOH solution of p_H 12.95.

H₂SO₄ solutions were prepared from the Analar product by appropriate dilutions with twice distilled water. Their concentrations were checked by the aid of a standard sodium carbonate solution. The buffer solutions of Clark and Lubs of p_H 3 to 9 and the Ringer buffer of p_H 12 were prepared as recommended by the respective authors and checked for their p_H values by the hydrogen electrode. The NaOH solution was prepared from a carbonate-free, highly concentrated solution by dilution with CO₂-free water and its p_H value estimated by the hydrogen electrode. The solutions were prepared from the Analar products by dissolving in water, twice distilled from alkaline permanganate.

Electrodes.—These were prepared from tellurium rods of 0.8 cm. in diameter provided by Scherring-Kahlbaum. A circular groove and two lateral ones were made at a distance of 1 cm from one end. A platinum wire was fitted well into the circular groove with its ends passing through the lateral ones. The end of the rod was then squeezed into a glass cup above which the platinum ends were sealed to the glass. Electrical contact was maintained through mercury and a copper wire. The apparent surface area of the electrode amounted to $\sim 8 \text{ cm}^2$. This was limited by making a circular groove around the rod at a distance of 3 cm from its lower end and dipping the electrode into the solution just to the groove. Before immersion, the electrode surface was rubbed by very fine emery paper, followed by filter paper, when it acquired a highly polished and smooth appearance.

Electrolysis Cell.—This was essentially similar to that of Bockris and Potter (*J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1952, **99**, 169; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, **20**, 614).

Procedures.—(A). The time—potential curves were constructed by using current densities ranging from 5×10^{-6} to 4×10^{-5} amps/cm². Prior to polarisation the electrode was left in contact with the solution, freed from oxygen by bubbling through it pure hydrogen, for a period of 30 minutes which was found sufficient for the attainment of thermal and electrochemical equilibrium. The polarisation process consisted in admitting the cathodic current for a period of 60 minutes till the attainment of constant potentials. The potential was then allowed to decay for a period of 30 minutes at the end of which the anodic current was applied. After 30 minutes the polarisation was stopped and the potential allowed to decay once more for a period of 30 minutes.

(B). For constructing the Tafel lines, the solutions were pre-electrolysed (Azzam *et al.*, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, **46**, 918) for a period of 20 hours using a current amounting in the average to 5 ma at the platinum electrode, followed by one-hour electrolysis at the tellurium electrode. The same results were obtained by carrying out the electrolysis for 10 hours, but for the sake of certainty the longer period was preferred. In tracing the Tafel lines, current densities ranging from 1×10^{-5} to 6×10^{-4} amps/cm² were applied. After constructing the Tafel lines from higher to lower currents, the p_{H} 's of the solutions were checked by the aid of a glass electrode except in the case of more concentrated acid solutions for which the p_{H} was calculated from the concentration using activity coefficients as given by Latimer ("Oxidation Potentials", Prentice Hall, N. Y., 1953, p. 354).

(A). **The Time-potential Curves.**—Representative time—potential curves at a current density of 4×10^{-5} amps/cm² at the p_{H} values 1.5, 4.98, 7.02 and 12.95 are shown in Fig. 1.

The curves obtained at current densities ranging from 5×10^{-6} to 4×10^{-5} amps/cm² in 0.1N-H₂SO₄ solution are represented in Fig. 2. These latter curves indicate that the behaviour varies with the current density applied both on cathodic and anodic polarisation. At the lower current densities, the curve is characterised by an initial rapid change to less positive potentials, followed by a less steep one before the attainment of constant values on the negative side of the hydrogen electrode slope. The decay curves exhibit an initial rapid change in potential to more positive values, followed by a less steep one, until they reach the initial potentials set before applying the polarising current.

FIG. 1

Cathodic and anodic polarisation curves of tellurium electrode at diff. p_H at 4×10^{-5} amps/cm².

(a-b) cathodic; (b-c) cathodic decay;
(c-d) anodic; (d-e) anodic decay.

1—0.1 N-H₂SO₄. 3— p_H 7.02.
2— p_H 4.98. 4— p_H 12.95.

FIG. 2

Cathodic and anodic polarisation curves of tellurium electrode in 0.1 N-H₂SO₄.

(a-b) cathodic; (b-c) cathodic decay;
(c-d) anodic; (d-e) anodic decay.

1—C.D. 5×10^{-6} amps/cm². 4—C.D. 3×10^{-5} amps/cm².
2— " 1×10^{-5} . 5— " 4×10^{-5} .
3— " 2.5×10^{-5} .

The same behaviour is manifested in the case of anodic polarisation and the decay which follows. The constant potentials attained during the anodic process and after decay are more positive than the initial potentials. A striking phenomenon is that the potentials, set at the constant regions during cathodic and anodic polarisation or cathodic and anodic decay, vary more or less regularly with the current density applied.

At higher current densities (e. g. 4×10^{-5} amps/cm²) only a single rapid rise in potential is observed (on cathodic polarisation) before attaining constant potential values at p_H 1.5 and 12.95. The less rapid change, which follows at lower currents, nearly disappears at these latter p_H 's and becomes less pronounced at p_H 4.98 and 7.02.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

(B). *The Tafel Lines.*—Fig. 3 shows the η — $\log i$ curves obtained by plotting the η values obtained at the end of the cathodic polarisation period against $\log i$ at p_H values 1.54, 4.98, 7.02 and 12.95. In Fig. 4 are shown the directly measured Tafel lines representing the behaviour in buffer solutions of p_H values 3.05, 4.98, 7.02, 8.92, 11.95 and 0.1 *N*-NaOH of p_H 12.95 within the C.D. range of 1×10^{-5} — 6×10^{-5} amps/cm². In Fig. 5 are shown representative Tafel lines obtained in sulphuric acid solutions of 2.9, 0.05 and 0.0115 *N*. Tafel lines for other acid concentrations lie in the vicinity of curve a (Fig. 5) and are then not easy to demonstrate.

FIG. 5

Tafel lines directly constructed
in H_2SO_4 solutions.

Curves a—c refer respectively to
2.9, 0.05 and 0.1 *N*- H_2SO_4 .

The Tafel lines in Figs. 3 and 4 are characterised by a single slope ranging between 0.031 and 0.046. The curves in Fig. 5, on the other hand, show two slopes. The first slope b_1 lying within the C. D. range 1×10^{-5} to 1×10^{-4} amounts to 0.04–0.052 volt, while the second slope b_2 occurs at higher current densities than 1×10^{-4} and varies from 0.07 to 0.1 volt within the acidity range 5 *N* to 0.05 *N*- H_2SO_4 (Table I). Higher slopes amounting to 0.3 volt are obtained in 0.0115 *N*- H_2SO_4 solutions (Fig. 5).

The parameters of the hydrogen overvoltage in the respective solution and the corresponding p_H values are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

H_2SO_4 conc. (<i>N</i>)...	4.89	2.9	0.98	0.49	0.05	0.0115
p_H ...	0.0097	0.39	0.89	1.14	2.22	2.76
b_1 ...	0.042	0.045	0.046	0.044	0.051	0.052
i_{01} ...	4×10^{-13}	8×10^{-12}	4.5×10^{-12}	2×10^{-11}	2×10^{-12}	1.5×10^{-10}
a ...	1.35	1.27	1.24	1.30	1.11	1.20
η at 2×10^{-5} (mV)	273	269	270	273	244	233
b_2 ...	0.074	0.098	0.084	0.07	0.118	0.32
i_{02} ...	1.6×10^{-9}	1×10^{-8}	3.5×10^{-9}	2.5×10^{-7}	4×10^{-7}	1.2×10^{-5}
a ...	0.77	0.57	0.69	0.69	0.77	...
η at 5×10^{-5} (mV)	358	361	353	343	391	539

In Table II are listed the parameters of the hydrogen overvoltage in the buffer solutions.

TABLE II

	Buffer solutions					
	HCl + phthalate.	NaOH + phthalate.	NaOH + phosphate	Boric + KCl+NaOH.	NaOH + phosphate.	0.1 N - NaOH.
ϕ_{π} ...	3.05	4.98	7.02	9.29	11.95	12.95
b ...	0.046	0.034	0.031	0.044	0.036	0.038
η at 10^{-5} amps/cm ² (mv)	312	288	240	160	28	28
a ...	0.95	1.04	1.23	1.84	...	...
$\Delta\eta/\Delta\phi_{\pi}$...	12	16	35	50	56	

DISCUSSION

Behaviour in 0.1 N-H₂SO₄ Solution: The Time-potential Curves.—The initial rapid change in potential to more negative values (Fig. 1) is apparently due to an IR drop. In conformity with this fact, the magnitude of the initial rise in potential increases with increasing current density, amounting thus to 200, 270 and 450 mv at 5×10^{-5} , 1×10^{-5} and 2×10^{-5} amps/cm² respectively. The slower change which follows includes reduction of the oxide film, formation of the double layer and the electrodeposition of hydrogen gas on the electrode surface. This latter section of the curve becomes less defined by increasing the current applied and disappears completely when the current amounts to 4×10^{-5} amps/cm². After complete reduction of the oxide film and build up of the double layer, the potential assumes constant values which vary in magnitude with the applied current, indicating that part of this potential is due to an overvoltage effect.

The potential changes which accompany the decay of the cathodic potentials are attributed to the breakdown of the cathodic double layer, the diffusion away or ionisation of hydrogen and the development of the oxide film on the electrode surface. In conformity with this fact, the potential set (+ 0.34 to + 0.37 volt) is intermediate between the values of both oxide and hydride systems, the E_0 values of which amount to + 0.53 and - 0.72 volt respectively.

The rapid rise in potential accompanying the application of the anodic current corresponds to further ionisation of hydrogen and formation of the anodic double layer. The less steep change following this part of the anodic curve, which is more pronounced at the lower currents applied (5×10^{-5} and 1×10^{-5} amps/cm²), is due to the deposition of oxygen with subsequent oxidation of the metal. When the electrode surface becomes completely covered with oxide, overlaid by oxygen, the potential assumes constant values which, as in the case of the cathodic potential, vary with the magnitude of the polarising current. This indicates that in both cases a part of the potential is originating from an overvoltage effect.

The decay of the anodic potential is accompanied with the collapse of the anodic double layer and the desorption of a certain amount of oxygen doublets before finally passing to a region which lies slightly positive to the metal—metal oxide potential. In this region also, the steady state potential is a function of current density and, as was previously stated, the electrode in its static condition is subject to an oxygen overvoltage effect which is smaller than when the anodic current is applied.

Behaviour in Solutions of different p_H .—In solutions of higher p_H than 1.5 (0.1N-H₂SO₄), the relation between current density and the initial drop in potential is the same as in the case of sulphuric acid solution. The slower change which follows becomes also less defined at a C. D. of 4×10^{-5} amps/cm² except in the case of p_H 4.98 and 7.02. This may find its origin in the stability of the oxide film within this p_H range, *i.e.* in the vicinity of the iso-electric point of tellurium dioxide (Issa and Awad, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 948) which lies at $\sim p_H$ 3.85 owing to the smaller solubility of the dioxide in these solutions as compared with the acid and alkaline ones. In these latter cases, the removal of the oxide is aided by the solvent action of the electrolyte, which is more apparent in the alkali solution. The steady states originating after anodic polarisation lie always more positive to the metal—metal oxide potentials and vary with the magnitude of the current as in the case of sulphuric acid solution. The steady state potentials at the cathodic and anodic regions are not only functions of current density at a given p_H , but like the static potentials and the potentials set after decay, are also function of p_H at a given current density.

The Tafel Lines.—The slope of the Tafel lines within the current density range $1 \times 10^{-5} - 1 \times 10^{-4}$ amps/cm² and amounting to 0.04 - 0.045 v indicates that within this current density range the process of hydrogen evolution on tellurium in sulphuric acid solutions of concentrations varying from 5 N to 0.5 N is governed by an electrochemical mechanism (Bockris *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Thus, as is well known for an electrochemical mechanism, the slope of the Tafel line is 0.04 and 0.118 v at lower and higher current densities respectively. At higher current densities the slope of the Tafel line lies between 0.07 and 0.118 v, indicating that within this current density range the evolution of hydrogen is governed either by an electrochemical or slow discharge mechanism (Bockris *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

In dilute sulphuric acid solutions of concentrations less than 0.05 N, there appears some resistance overpotential leading to a rapid increase in the value of the slope of the Tafel line above a current density of 8×10^{-5} amps/cm². This resistance overpotential is but small at lower current densities where the slope of the Tafel line amounts to 0.05 v.

The Tafel lines obtained in buffer solutions and in 0.1 N sodium hydroxide (Table II; Fig. 5), constructed within the current density range 1×10^{-5} to 6×10^{-5} amps/cm², possess the same slopes as in the case of sulphuric acid solutions for the same current density range. This indicates a similar mechanism for the evolution of hydrogen and that anions have no effect on the process of hydrogen evolution. Tafel lines constructed from the time—potential curves by considering the steady state potentials set after one hour (Fig. 3) possess, on the other hand, slopes amounting to 0.052 - 0.07 v, which are higher than the directly traced ones. This is apparently due to the presence of impurities since the solutions were not pre-electrolysed prior to the passage of the current.